

A Study on Digitalization and Economic Growth

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Abstract

Digitalization less commonly known as digitization is a process of converting any form of information in a digital form. Digitalization has been proved as a smart changing trend in the businesses. With the adoption of digitalization there's been a massive impact on the products. The following paper aims at analysing the chief and relevant changes taking place of the product life cycle in marketing through Digitalization. Product Life Cycle gives a complete rundown of a product right from its new tiny feet in the market to its expiry. The Product Life Cycle is elaborated through its four steps Introduction, Growth, Maturity and Decline. This process is used to monitor the product life in the running market. The paper focuses on the recent changes occurring in PLC through digitalization. The author finds that marketing promotions and the sales of any products are the higher scales when compared with the previous years through digitalization, research on well liked commercial products. The research paper provides the solution for- how digitalization helps in the growth of a products, how impactful is digitalization on economic growth. The research evokes the extension of PLC with new strategies and results. Therefore the paper give a route to a companies destination i.e success with the occurrence of digitalization in marketing. Through the past cases and future pro's and cons.

Keywords: Digitization, PLC Evolution, Marketing Blueprint, Benefaction, Market, Affluent Business, Thriving Products, Constructive Changes.

Introduction

Product life cycle was developed by Raymond Vernon an economist in 1966. PLC has been brought into the field of economics and marketing. Product Life Cycle describes a complete rundown of a product right from its new tiny feet in the market to its expiry or death.

According to Raymond Vernon the products are classified into three categories based on their stage in the product life cycle. Also by considering their progress in the International Trade Markets :

- New Product
- Maturing Product
- Standardized Product

international product life cycle

based on: Raymond Vernon, 1966. *International investment and international trade in the product cycle*, The Quarterly Journal of Economics, 80(2), pp. 190-207

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The Product Life Cycle is Elaborated through it's Four Steps

- Introduction
- Growth
- Maturity and
- Decline

In the first stage the new product is launched in the market, where the customers are totally unaware about the product. To create a buzz about the product and publicize it, producers start with it's promotion to stimulate sales. At this stage, the product has minimal profit and there are only a few competitors. As more units of the product sell, it enters the next stage automatically.

In the second stage the demand of the product increase which leads to increase in sales. As a result the entire production cost minimises and the profit increases. This is the phase where the company has competition as new competitors enter the market with their own unique products. To cope up the competition the company increase their expense on promotional doings to increase the sales and gain new customers. As the sales and customers increases the product goes to the next stage.

In the third stage of PLC the product is widely known by the customers. The demands slower comes down and the sales increases but in slower rates. Looking at the competition the company may cut down it’s profit to sustain itself in the market. But the business remains catchy and company spends of it’s promotions. To add on the demand of the product grows in the others countries.

The forth stage occurs when the product tops in the third stage and then begins a downward slope slide in sales. As a result the revenues drop to a level where it makes no sense to continue producing the product. Investment is minimised. The manufacturing of the product is discontinued, or it is sold to another company. Production may shift to the developing countries. But the Labor wages again play a vital role, as the developed countries are busy introducing other products. On costs and revenues: When the production costs goes high and the demand of the product is low, it is no more offered on the market for a long run and eventually, is withdrawn from the market in the “decline” stage.

Digitalization in Product Life Cycle

Digitalization less popularly known as digitization has been a boon in the business industries. In the field of marketing, digitalization has made drastic changes in the trade markets and have boosted the economy of companies. The PLC management created through digitalization has brought a rise in the marketing strategies. With the adoption of digitalization there’s has been a massive impact on the products. It has become an essential tool for hundreds of manufacturing companies. Today, majority of the companies are dependent of the PLC management. If a company fails to adopt a digital strategy for PLC there may be chances for the complete to dissolve soon or get washed away from the competition.

Review of Literature

- **Kellogg’s Nutri-Grain Case Study:**

In 1997 Kellogg’s had achieved great success with the approximation of 50% in less than three years. The sale continued till 2002 with an increase of flavours. Taking an example nutri gain was one amongst their products and had well competitors. Nutri gain invested years in the growth stage itself. In the middle of 2004 they found the product terribly failing. At this phase the company had to make a decision, either they could withdraw the product i.e nutri gain or improve on it. ~ **the times 100, 2009**

- **Nestle Maggi**

Maggi was launched back in 1980’s in the Indian market. The product was launched keeping children and working women in mind. Maggi was a pioneer in the instant noodles market. In the initial stage of growth a huge amount was spent on marketing through digital methods, with the tag of ready to eat noodles. Thus there was a drastic increase in the sales and their profits rose high like never before. Coming to its third stage in 1990’s maggi faced a tough competition from Top Ramen and many new competitors. Yet maggi was still in the rum. Till the product got temporarily banned due to it’s high lead content. The product sales fell down and the profits were cut. There were a lot of research done by the company while it’s hard times to prove themselves till the ban was abandoned. The company had a turn over slowly in the market and gained the an initial tag again. Till day the company has not come to it’s decline stage as it keeps introducing new varieties and product lines. ~**Blogspot.com, Wednesday, 4 September 2013.**

Objectives

1. To study the impact and the positive growth of the forthcoming product life cycle revolution.
2. Automate monotonous business activities.
3. To investigate the Innovation in product life cycle which are creating productivity opportunities for business and the economy.
4. Reshaping of a products life cycle and the future of marketing strategies

Limitation

1. Time bound
2. Our research is purely based on Digitalization and economic growth which does not aid any of the other sector.
3. A systematic search for the data was conducted based on the research papers published between 2006-2017.

Statement of the Problem

- The situations and the environment varies from one place to the other. Therefore the same PLC strategies may not suitable for every company and it's location.
- PLC analysis cannot be applied on all the products. If taken an example: it cannot be applied on mobile networking or computer software products as their adaptation is dynamic in nature as there are frequent updates
- The 4p's of marketing also create variations in the PLC
- The product life cycle process includes lot if research and analysis of the product sales which indeed is time consuming and times the data is unavailable

Research Methodology

We aim to provide our understanding on the basis of the collected secondary data and present our insights and understanding about the impact of digitalization and economic growth in the field of product life cycle in marketing as per the recent trends and statistics.

Data Analysis

April 25, 2011

When we talk about data analysis one of the examples can be the very well renowned Brand, company Apple. Right from the I pod to the I pad the apple product life cycle has a rapid growth potential. Their products life cycle shows that their products are going to be on a massive hype in the further coming years.

The ipod took nearly 5 years to break thirty million units record. iPhone took 4 years and Ipad shall take 2 years from it's launch. On the other hand side Sony Walkman could never achieve that growth even after 10 years of their life cycle.

As seen apple products are growing faster and higher in less time span comparing the past. The ipod sales went to the peak in the year 2008 under 55 million units. Along with the iPhones selling it's 70 million units. It's estimated that the company shall have a rise over 100 billion dollars in 2011.

As we know the plc has four main stages which is introduction, growth, maturity and decline.

Looking at the progress we can surly tell the four trade changing years of massive growth of apple products from the ipod to Ipad were set to sell million units per year in 2012 and 2014. Despite of having good competition with the androids. Apple has comparatively better PLC management strategies which undoubtedly shows their success as a result. ~ April 25, 2011 at 06:13 PM in

Apple Case Study - iPod to the iPad, Corporate Strategy, Current Affairs, Economics, iPad market share, jkaonline | Permalink.

Findings

- With the massive changes in the stream of technology we see, it's now important to generate innovative ideas to launch in the market quickly. Since the forth revolution shall bring drastic change when compared to the past years with the help of PLC if not the companies shall face death. ~ **says Tony Hemmelgarn, chief executive of Siemens PLM Software.**
- Product life cycle process is now the soul if digital firms. Also it has newly expected it's self in the innovation management and in product commercialisation with modern solution
- Product life cycle is no more a simple individual process rather it has fresh components of a wider supply chain solution for various products and organizations. ~**says John Kelley, vice president of product value chain strategy at Oracle.**
- Companies have now started to implement PLC management data into realistic meaningful analysis or insights. Also how effectively can a firm connect with it's customers. ~ **says Ramprasad Srinivasan, UK technical PLM expert at PwC**

Conclusion

If the PLC analysis with the essence of digitalization is done right, this will warn the companies about the results of their products they serve to the public. This process will also help the companies to know it's pro's and con's about thier product and will allow them to make right decisions for their betterment.

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